

C-S and C-N coupling reactions of barbituric acid via selective and complete bromination using greener KBr/H₂O₂ as a brominating agent

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Manuscript received 05 March 2018, revised 16 March 2018, accepted 11 April 2018

1,3-Disubstituted/unsubstituted barbituric acids on treatment with KBr-H₂O₂ as a greener brominating reagent give mono and dibromo barbituric acids. With aqueous HCl selective bromination and without aqueous HCl complete bromination of active methylene group of barbituric acids took place. The reaction of monobarbituric acids with thiosemicarbazide and thioglyoxalic acid under refluxing in aqueous medium, simple C-S coupling products were obtained. The spiro C-N coupling product was obtained by the interaction of dibromo barbituric acid with thiosemicarbazide and C-N condensation product was obtained by the interaction of dibromo barbituric acid with guanidine nitrate, both reactions took place in aqueous medium under refluxing conditions. An environmentally benign, aqueous mediated C-S and C-N organic transformation by the interaction of barbituric acids mediated by KBr-H₂O₂ as a greener brominating reagent is described. The simple product workup, use of inexpensive greener reagent KBr-H₂O₂ for bromination and simple purification without column are the additional advantages of synthetic protocol.

Keywords: Mono and dibromo barbituric acids, KBr/H₂O₂ greener brominating agent, C-S and C-N coupling products.

Introduction

The carbon sulfur bonds are prevalent present in organic compounds and have numerous applications like medicinally important natural products, biologically active drugs, paints, and spectroscopic probes^{1,2}. Therefore, in the recent era, C-S coupling reaction has been of immense importance in organic synthesis and researchers developed diverse cross coupling methodologies for pharmaceuticals. Some important methods involved in the reduction of aryl sulfones or aryl sulfoxides using strong reducing agents like DIBALH or LiAlH₄³, thiol addition to α,β unsaturated carbonyl compounds at RT⁴. In 1980, Migita *et al.* have reported the Pd catalyzed thiation of aryl bromides using Pd(PPh₃)₄⁵. Subsequently, other metals like nickel⁶, copper⁷, cobalt⁸, iron⁹,

rhodium¹⁰, and manganese¹¹ have also been employed. The bromination of active methylene compounds is an important electrophilic substitution in organic synthesis. These important classes of compounds are useful synthetic intermediates for various transformations¹²⁻¹⁶, especially, α -bromo carbonyl compounds have become an important motif for the development of various biologically active compounds¹⁷⁻²¹. The selective bromination of carbonyl compounds have been challenging task, because monosubstituted is main product but small amount of disubstituted product is also produced as an impurity during the reaction^{22,23}. Literature survey revealed that the synthesis of α -halo carbonyl compounds is a challenge for organic chemists in 19th century hence considerable efforts have been taken for development of various useful reagents²⁴⁻²⁷.

Barbituric acids and their derivatives have received a lot of attention over the years because of their structural importance in organic transformation²⁸. They have also exhibited biological, pharmaceutical applications. Barbituric acid has an “active” methylene group²⁹, that act as key precursor in the various organic transformations³⁰⁻³². Here we wish to report the efficient and greener methods for selective and complete bromination for active methylene group followed by simple C-S coupling reaction demonstrated in present protocol (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

This is the first report of a simple, inexpensive, and fairly efficient catalyst free synthesis of selective and complete bromination of barbiturates. We attempted reaction of barbituric acid and KBr in H₂O₂

with or without HCl on stirring in organic solvent. We obtained the desired 5-bromo and 5,5'-dibromo barbituric acids in varying proportion of KBr in H₂O₂ under different conditions and progress of reaction was monitored by TLC.

Initially, we examined the reaction in water medium on stirring the 1:1 mole barbituric acid and KBr with HCl for 24 h, 5-bromobarbituric acid was obtained with poor yield (Table 1, entry 1) and is soluble in water so that it made difficult to isolate the product. When we attempted the same reaction in different solvent like ethanol, ethylene glycol, DMF and DCM on stirring and or reflux conditions but we did not get any desirable impact (Table 1, entry 2-5). The non polar solvent like toluene was used and vigorous reaction took place with very good impact (Table 1, entry 6). We realized that a good amount

Scheme 1

of product was obtained when we changed stoichiometry ratio such as 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5. Interestingly, the reaction was achieved most effectively under stirring with 1:5 mole which yielded 85% of 5-bromobarbituric acid after 24 h. We applied the same concept for complete bromination using 1:5 mole of barbituric acid and KBr in H₂O₂ without HCl, which yielded 84% of 5,5'-dibromo barbituric acid after 24 h (Table 2, entry 2). Finally we have also tried reaction in ethyl alcohol, ethylene glycol, dichloromethane and dimethyl formamide but no appreciable yield was obtained.

We have further carried out C-S coupling reaction of mono and dibromo barbituric acids with guanidine nitrate, thiosemicarbazide, and thioglyoxalic acid using water as a greener solvent under reflux conditions and experimental results are summarized. All synthesized products were characterized on the basis ¹H NMR and chemical identity of product was confirmed by elemental test and layer test. Finally, we have compared our results with green chemistry metrics in relation to efficiency and capability of the present protocol and we have compared and found comparable with principles of green chemistry. Zero value of Solvent and Catalyst Environmental Impact (SCEI) suggested that reactions completely follow green chemistry principle (Table 3).

Experimental

Synthesis of 5-bromo-barbituric acid (2):

A mixture aqueous solution of barbituric acids (0.001 mol) and potassium bromide (0.005 mol) in 100 ml RB flask was stirred by adding 30% hydrogen peroxide (0.02 mol) and 1 mL HCl solution (0.005 mol). The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was isolated by simple filtration and further purified by recrystallization using water with a good yield.

Synthesis of 5,5'-dibromo-barbituric acid (3):

A mixture of aqueous solution of barbituric acid (0.001 mol) and potassium bromide (0.005 mol) in 100 ml RB flask was stirred by adding 30% hydrogen peroxide (0.02 mol). The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the product was isolated by simple filtration

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions for selective bromination

E	S	Mole proportion of reactant											
		1:1		1:2		1:3		1:4		1:5			
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B		
1	W	24	15	24	18	24	20	24	22	24	33	24	24
2	EA	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-
3	EG	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-
4	DCM	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-
5	DMF	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-	24	-
6	To	24	18	24	25	24	44	24	60	24	85	24	24

where A-stirring, B-reflux, E-entry, T-time in hour, W-water, To-toluene, EA-ethyl alcohol, EG-ethylene glycol, DCM-dichloromethane, DMF-dimethylformamide, S-solvent, Y-yield in %.

Table 2. Optimization of reaction conditions for complete bromination

E	S	Mole proportion of reactant																
		1:1		1:2		1:3		1:4		1:5								
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B							
1	W	24	5	24	22	24	24	15	24	24	24	24	34	24	24	75	24	-
2	To	24	65	24	68	24	24	73	24	24	24	24	80	24	24	84	24	-

where A-stirring, B-reflux, E-entry, T-time in hour, To-toluene, W-water, S-solvent, Y-yield in %.

and further purified by recrystallization using water with a good yield.

Synthesis of 1-amino-2-(6-hydroxy-2,4-dioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-yl)isothiourea (4):

A mixture of 5-bromo barbituric acid (0.001 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.001 mol) in water (2–3 mL) was refluxed in 100 ml RB flask for 2.0 h. The completion of reaction has been identified by TLC. The product was isolated by simple workup and solid residue washed with hot water followed by brine. Orange solid was obtained with negative desulphurization test and product was further purified by recrystallization in ethanol. Yield 0.06 g (46.15%), m.p. 200°C; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 12.7 (1H, s, OH); 10.9 (1H, s, NH), 10.1 (2H, s, NH₂-N), 9.8 (2H, s, NH₂-N), 6.6 (1H, s, -NH); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 60.8, 150.4, 155.1, 160.9, 190.3.

Synthesis of [1,4]oxathiino[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2,4,7(1H,3H,6H)-trione (5):

A mixture of 5-bromo barbituric acid (0.002 mol) and thioglyoxalic acid (0.002 mol) in water (2–3 mL) was refluxed in 100 ml RB flask for 2.5 h. The completion of reaction has been identified by TLC. The product was isolated by simple workup and solid residue washed with hot water followed by brine. White solid product was obtained with negative desulphurization test and further purified by recrystallization in ethanol with good yield. Yield 0.11 g (84.61%), m.p. >360°C; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 7.0 (1H, s, NH), 4.3 (1H, s, CH-S), 3.4 (2H, s, S-CH₂-CO); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 26.5, 52.3, 151.7, 158.4, 168.1, 171.6.

Synthesis of 1,3-dimethyl-[1,4]oxathiino[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2,4,7(1H,3H,6H)-trione (6):

A mixture of 5-bromo-N,N-dimethyl barbituric acid (0.002 mol) and thioglyoxalic acid (0.002 mol) in water (2–3 mL) was refluxed in 100 ml RB flask for 3 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the product was isolated by simple filtration and solid residue washed with hot water followed by brine. The pale green solid mass was obtained with positive desulphurization test and purified by recrystallized in ethanol with insufficient yield. Yield 0.05 g (38.46%), m.p. 260°C; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6): δ 3.4

Table 3. Green chemistry metrics applied for C-S coupling reactions

P	% AE	Kernel RME	Curzon RME	Andrus RME	MI	MP	% CE	E factor	% AU	SCEI
4	72.86	0.6631	0.6631	0.1675	5.97	16.75	100	0.37	72.86	0
5	66.92	0.5956	0.5956	0.1542	6.48	15.42	100	0.4942	66.92	0
6	69.76	0.4953	0.4953	0.1720	5.81	17.20	100	0.4334	69.76	0
7	64.23	0.4881	0.4881	0.2150	4.65	21.50	100	0.1798	64.23	0
8	52.83	0.4860	0.4860	0.1447	6.90	14.47	100	0.8927	52.83	0

where Product (P), Atom economy (AE), Reaction mass efficiency (RME), Mass intensity (MI), Mass productivity (MP), Carbon efficiency (CE), Environmental factor (E factor), Atom utilization (AU), Solvent and Catalyst Environmental Impact (SCEI).

(2H, s, S-CH₂-CO), 3.1 (3H, s, CH₃-N), 3.0 (3H, s, CH₃-N).

Synthesis of 8-imino-1H-purine-2,6(3H,8H)-dione (7):

A mixture of 5,5'-bromo barbituric acid (0.002 mol) and guanidine nitrate (0.002 mol) in water (2–3 mL) was refluxed in 100 ml RB flask for 24 h. After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, product was work up with brine, and isolated by simple filtration to afford condensation crude product. The crude product was further purified by recrystallization in ethanol to obtain product with good yield. Yield 0.67 g (76%), m.p. 160°C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 7.0 (2H, s, NHCO), 5.4 (1H, s, C=NH); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 149.1, 153.4, 159.9, 163.2.

Synthesis of 1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-trioxo-hexahydro-pyrimidine-5,5'-(1,2,4-triazolidine-thione) (8):

A mixture of 5,5'-bromo-N,N-dimethyl barbituric acid (0.002 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mol) in water (2–3 mL) was refluxed in 100 ml RB flask for 24 h. After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, dimethylation followed by spiro compound was obtained. Solid product was work up with brine, and isolated by simple filtration to afford crude product. The crude product was further purified by recrystallization in ethanol to obtain highly functionalized cyclized product. Yield 0.81 g (90%), m.p. 135°C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 8.6 (1H, s, NHCO), 7.6 (1H, s, NHCO), 7.1 (1H, s, NH-C=S), 4.5 (2H, s, NH-NH-C=S); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆): δ 23.3, 82.7, 143.8, 171.3, 182.2.

Plausible mechanism:

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have reported an efficient, catalyst free C-S coupling reaction via selective and complete bromination of active methylene group of barbituric acid using greener solvent and reagent. This method not only offers substantial improvements in the reaction rates, yields and also avoids the use of hazardous solvents and catalyst. The green chemistry metrics have exhibited the environmental efficiency and capability of this protocol.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. S. G. Charalwar, Principal, Shri M. M. College of Science, Nagpur for encouragement and providing necessary facilities.

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